

Submission from the National Open Science Taskforce (NOST) to the Strategic Examination of Research and Development Discussion Paper

About us	2
Contact	2
Executive Summary	2
Submission to the Strategic Examination of Research and Development discussion paper	4
Action 1 - Development and Implementation of a National Open Science Action Plan. and the incentives to support Open Science	4
Action 2 - Infrastructure to support open publishing and dissemination through the establishment of a central repository for the sharing of research outputs and the establishment of infrastructure to support Diamond Open Access journals (free to publish, free to read) at scale	6
Action 3 - Improving the legal infrastructure around research publications and data at the institutional level	9
Action 4 - Embedding of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Knowledge in mainstream knowledge systems	14

Submission to the Strategic Examination of Research and Development discussion paper

About us

This submission is made on behalf of the National Open Science Taskforce (NOST). Established in 2024, with membership drawn from Australian research academies, research funders and expert bodies engaged in the production, management and use of publicly funded research, the Taskforce provides expert and informed advice on issues related to Open Science.

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Executive Summary

This submission to the Strategic Examination of Research and Development discussion paper [<https://consult.industry.gov.au/strategic-examination-rd-discussion-paper>] is created by the National Open Science Taskforce (NOST) and addresses: *Question 4. What types of funding sources, models and/or infrastructure are currently missing or should be expanded for Australian R&D?*

Open Science is a key enabler of the takeup of publicly funded research worldwide. Australia lacks sovereign capability in infrastructure and policy to enable Open Science, leaving us increasingly lagging behind comparative economies.

We are calling for action in the following four areas:

1. Development and Implementation of a National Open Science Action Plan and the incentives to support Open Science
2. Infrastructure to support open publishing and dissemination through the establishment of a central repository for the sharing of research outputs and the establishment of infrastructure to support Diamond Open Access journals (free to publish, free to read) at scale
3. Improving the legal infrastructure around research publications and data at the institutional level
4. Embedding of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Island Indigenous Knowledges in mainstream knowledge systems

Action 1 - Development and Implementation of a National Open Science Action Plan and the incentives to support Open Science.

Australia currently lacks any national plan to coordinate the delivery of Open Science. **A national approach, coordinated with a modernised approach to research assessment, would ensure that Australia is well-placed to maximise the impact of its research.** This impact can be facilitated through implementing policies on:

1. Open Access and Open Science
2. Research Assessment

Action 2 - Infrastructure to support open publishing and dissemination through the establishment of a central repository for the sharing of research outputs and the establishment of infrastructure to support Diamond Open Access journals (free to publish, free to read) at scale

The lack of investment in a national Open Science research infrastructure over the past few decades now poses serious sovereign risk through the encroachment of huge commercial interests into the university sector. This can be mitigated by investment in [open infrastructure](https://oaaustralasia.org/open-access-australasia-2022-election-statement/) [https://oaaustralasia.org/open-access-australasia-2022-election-statement/] in the form of:

1. A migration roadmap to a national research repository
2. National infrastructure for academic-led open publishing

Action 3 - Improving the legal infrastructure around research publications and data at the institutional level

Law and regulation are an essential part of research infrastructure, however the legislative frameworks we have are not well designed to serve the Australian research community or facilitate research translation. Australia has many more barriers to sharing research, research data and building collaborations than comparator countries due to three related factors:

1. No effective rights retention
2. Outdated IP commercialisation metrics
3. Poor understanding of the wider legal infrastructure supporting research collaboration

Action 4 - Embedding of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Knowledge in mainstream knowledge systems

Addressing the current fragmented approach to the inclusion of Indigenous Knowledge to embed Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander research processes in the R&D system requires a deeper consideration of:

1. Improved protection of Indigenous Cultural and Intellectual Property (ICIP) and Indigenous data sovereignty
2. Indigenous governance of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Knowledge

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Action 1 - Development and Implementation of a National Open Science Action Plan. and the incentives to support Open Science

Australia currently lacks any national plan to coordinate the delivery of Open Science. A **national approach, coordinated with an approach to research assessment, would ensure that Australia is well placed to maximise the impact of its research.** These can be addressed through implementing policies on:

1. Open Access and Open Science
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1. Open Access and Open Science

Open Science is a key missing link in enabling the take-up by business, industry, government and other end-users of Australian publicly funded research. In this regard, Australia is lagging far behind similar economies. The Strategic Examination of R&D provides a unique opportunity to consider the pathways for collaboration and information sharing that will harness the full value and impact of Australian R&D.

The UK, EU, North and South American and Asian countries have effected significant changes to research culture and removed impediments to collaboration through implementing adoption of Open Science. A global shift to Open Science, including access to Open Data, is being achieved through international collaboration and national plans, spearheaded through the [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science) (2022)[<https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science>] , the [EU's Open Science Policy](https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/open-science_en) [https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/open-science_en] , the [US Co-ordination of Open Science](https://www.science.gov/Open-Science-Public-Access.html) [<https://www.science.gov/Open-Science-Public-Access.html>] through the (previous US President's) White House Office of Science and Technology, the [Canadian Government's Open Science Action Plan](https://www.canada.ca/en/environment-climate-change/services/science-technology/open-science-action-plan.html) [<https://www.canada.ca/en/environment-climate-change/services/science-technology/open-science-action-plan.html>], and the [Japan Science and Technology Open Access to Research Publications and Research Data Management](https://www.jst.go.jp/EN/about/openscience/policy_openscience_en_r4.pdf) [https://www.jst.go.jp/EN/about/openscience/policy_openscience_en_r4.pdf].

There have been repeated calls for action on Open Access and Open Science in Australia, for example, from the Productivity Commission in 2017 (which was [supported by the Government](https://www.pc.gov.au/inquiries/completed/intellectual-property/intellectual-property-government-response.pdf) [<https://www.pc.gov.au/inquiries/completed/intellectual-property/intellectual-property-government-response.pdf>]) and in 2023. The Australian Academy of Science has had a [statement on Open Science](https://www.science.org.au/supporting-science/science-policy-and-analysis/position-statements/position-statement-open-science) [<https://www.science.org.au/supporting-science/science-policy-and-analysis/position-statements/position-statement-open-science>] since 2021; Open Access Australasia has had calls for national Open Access and now Open Science approaches since 2013

[\[https://oaaustralasia.org/advocacy/#submissions\]](https://oaaustralasia.org/advocacy/#submissions) and the Council of Australasian University Librarians has developed increasingly stronger calls for action, the [latest in 2024](#) [\[https://www.chiefscientist.gov.au/news-and-media/advice-open-access-models\]](https://www.chiefscientist.gov.au/news-and-media/advice-open-access-models). Despite these activities, there has been no coordinated sector-wide approach on Open Access or Open Science.

The previous Chief Scientist proposed [a plan for Open Access](#), [\[https://www.chiefscientist.gov.au/news-and-media/advice-open-access-models\]](https://www.chiefscientist.gov.au/news-and-media/advice-open-access-models) which did not proceed given mixed sector support and was not adopted by the Federal Government. One concern about this model was how it would have entrenched the role of large commercial publishers in the Open Access system in Australia, to the exclusion of a diversity of models (see below on Open Access infrastructure).

In 2022, Australia ratified the UNESCO Open Science Recommendation, but since then, the Australian Government has provided no coordination or national infrastructure to support its implementation. Activity on the Open Science Recommendation in Australia has come entirely from advocacy groups as [Open Access Australasia](#) [\[https://oaaustralasia.org/\]](https://oaaustralasia.org/), [CAUL](#) [\[https://www.caul.edu.au/\]](https://www.caul.edu.au/) [\[https://www.caul.edu.au/\]](https://www.caul.edu.au/) or through the actions of individual institutions or universities NOST (National Open Science Taskforce) originated from an Academy of the Social Sciences in Australia Policy Roundtable - [Roadmap for Open Research](#) meeting held in June 2024 [\[https://socialsciences.org.au/events/australian-roadmap-for-open-research/\]](https://socialsciences.org.au/events/australian-roadmap-for-open-research/). The meeting invited subject matter expert representation of all organisations and government departments with an interest in improving the knowledge ecosystem to facilitate research collaboration and the sharing of research. The meeting concluded with a call for national leadership and action.

2. Research Assessment

Successive Australian Governments have identified a gap between Australia's research excellence, identified in terms of research quality as indicated by citations and university rankings, and the (lack of) translation of research as achieved by some comparator countries:

- National research priorities have not significantly influenced Australia's research profile.
- Programs linking research to business have barely changed the dial. (Discussion Paper, p.10)

Research assessment is intimately entwined with Open Science, research quality and the effective translation of research.

The dominance of large international publishers and indexing organisations has led to an overdominance of journal articles and, by extension, journals themselves as measures of quality in research.

However, it is now well accepted from international activities such as [DORA](#) [\[https://sfdora.org/\]](https://sfdora.org/) and [CoARA](#) [\[https://coara.eu/\]](https://coara.eu/) that journal metrics, such as citations or which quartiles a journal falls into within ranking systems, are a poor proxy for the quality of research and are an even worse proxy for the assessment of researchers. Such metrics also cannot be compared across disciplines and any such comparisons specifically disadvantage some disciplines such as those in humanities and Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander research. A recent [global survey](#) [\[https://stories.springernature.com/state-of-research-assessment/\]](https://stories.springernature.com/state-of-research-assessment/) by Springer Nature found "that [metrics-based evaluations are still dominant](#)

[\[https://stories.springernature.com/state-of-research-assessment/current-status/index.html#section-Use-of-metrics-J8DFFSua6D\]](https://stories.springernature.com/state-of-research-assessment/current-status/index.html#section-Use-of-metrics-J8DFFSua6D) – and often narrowly focused on journal publications with little consideration for the other outputs they produce (e.g. datasets).” The survey also found that researchers’ positive [contributions to society](https://stories.springernature.com/state-of-research-assessment/current-status/index.html#group-section-Contributions-to-society-i7ge5qA7K2) [\[https://stories.springernature.com/state-of-research-assessment/current-status/index.html#group-section-Contributions-to-society-i7ge5qA7K2\]](https://stories.springernature.com/state-of-research-assessment/current-status/index.html#group-section-Contributions-to-society-i7ge5qA7K2) “if considered, are not weighted as highly as research outputs.”

Importantly, journal metrics also do not provide insight into how open the research is or how reproducible or reliable it is.

Previous ERA activities run by the ARC primarily focused on the number of research publications. Notably, no national research assessment activity has existed for seven years. The addition of Engagement and Impact Assessment in 2018 was an attempt to capture the broader impact of research, but it is arguable whether it achieved its aim, and it placed a very high burden on institutions to report. A [report from ACOLA](https://acola.org/research-assessment/) [\[https://acola.org/research-assessment/\]](https://acola.org/research-assessment/) on research assessment commissioned by the previous Chief Scientist noted that “The current system used to evaluate and assess research careers for hiring, promotion and funding, is inadequate and does not serve its intended purpose effectively.”

There is an opportunity now for a fundamental rethink of how research is assessed in Australia, which takes a holistic approach to research impact. It needs to have an inclusive approach encompassing the many types of research outputs: articles, books, datasets, outputs from the humanities and social sciences, and also to recognise the myriad activities of researchers. One such approach is that from the Netherlands with recognises diverse research activities and outputs: “[Room for everyone's talent](https://www.nwo.nl/en/position-paper-room-for-everyones-talent)” [\[https://www.nwo.nl/en/position-paper-room-for-everyones-talent\]](https://www.nwo.nl/en/position-paper-room-for-everyones-talent) A similar approach developed for the Australian sector could include multiple dimensions of impact, including academic, social, political and, if appropriate, commercial impact. It could also include a robust assessment of how reproducible the research is.

Action 2 - Infrastructure to support open publishing and dissemination through the establishment of a central repository for the sharing of research outputs and the establishment of infrastructure to support Diamond Open Access journals (free to publish, free to read) at scale

The lack of investment in a national Open Research infrastructure over the past few decades now poses serious sovereign risk through the encroachment of huge commercial interests into the university sector. This can be mitigated by investment infrastructure in the form of:

1. A migration roadmap to a national research repository
2. National infrastructure for academic-led open publishing

There is an imperative for Australia to regain sovereign control over its research outputs and information about its research, both of which are increasingly being captured by a small number of huge commercial interests. These companies began as commercial publishing companies but, through targeted and relentless vertical acquisition agendas, have become behemoths in the industry. The

largest of these are Clarivate and RELX. RELX is the parent company of Elsevier and 40% of revenue comes from databases and tools according to the 2022 RELX annual report.

Australian dependency on multinational publishers is increasing as the market quickly consolidates - the top 20 largest publishers controlled 83% of the corpus in 2022. The former Chief Scientist of Australia, Dr Cathy Foley, argued in her [Advice on Open Access](https://www.chiefscientist.gov.au/news-and-media/advice-open-access-models) [https://www.chiefscientist.gov.au/news-and-media/advice-open-access-models] that publisher paywalls harm innovation and SME enterprises in particular. In 2024, 56% of Australian publications [remained closed access](https://open.coki.ac/) [https://open.coki.ac/]. Models identified for redressing this include a [consideration of rights retention](https://www.chiefscientist.gov.au/sites/default/files/2024-08/Addendum%20to%20open%20access%20advice%202024.pdf) [https://www.chiefscientist.gov.au/sites/default/files/2024-08/Addendum%20to%20open%20access%20advice%202024.pdf]. While overall rates of open access are increasing in Australia, the gains are in paid open publishing models at the expense of other [more financially sustainable models](https://www.iastatedigitalpress.com/jlsc/article/id/18317/) [https://www.iastatedigitalpress.com/jlsc/article/id/18317/]. There is an urgent need for a **clear understanding of the extent of the commercial take-over of our nationally publicly funded research outputs and institutional repositories (IR), as well as a risk analysis that assesses the implications for sovereign Australian research infrastructure.**

The 2001 Systemic Infrastructure Initiative invested in research data as infrastructure with multiple initiatives, now consolidated into the Australian Research Data Commons. While Australia now has infrastructure around research data, this is only one aspect of Open Science, with the remaining areas lagging behind in investment, support and integration. There are two areas requiring urgent attention:

1. A migration roadmap to a national research repository

An open-access repository is a database or a virtual archive established to collect, disseminate and preserve scientific outputs, such as scientific articles, and make them freely available. Repositories can be linked to a funder, such as the National Institutes of Health's PubMed Central [https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/] and its partner Europe PMC [https://europepmc.org/], to a region, such as OpenAire [https://www.openaire.eu/where-can-i-read-more-about-fp7] or to a nation [Scholaris](https://scholaris.ca/) [https://scholaris.ca/] in Canada, to a research field or subject, or to an institution, such as Cambridge University's repository, Apollo [https://www.repository.cam.ac.uk/home]. Repositories are a well-established and internationally embraced mechanism for capturing and disseminating research outputs. They are collated together into global aggregators such as CORE [https://core.ac.uk/], which indexes the world's repositories and links to 335 million open outputs.

Currently Australia has some repository infrastructure at the institutional level, but **no repository software at a national level**. Attempts to identify the nature of Australia's repository network have been made over the past decade, but are incomplete. One example is [the list maintained by Open Access Australasia](https://oaaustralasia.org/directories/) [https://oaaustralasia.org/directories/].

The software underpinning repositories at institutions is often commercial, owned by a few companies – Clarivate, Elsevier/RELX and Digital Science (whose parent company is Springer Nature). Essential research infrastructure for our publicly funded research is being pulled into a very small number of commercial hands. There is an urgent need for a clear understanding of the extent of the commercial takeover by foreign organisations of our national publicly funded research outputs and scholarly

infrastructure that contains the metadata and information about the entirety of Australian research engagement and enterprise.

The **solution is a central repository based on an open-source platform that can be used nationwide to develop an open collection of all research outputs generated by Australian researchers**. The Canadian example of [Scholaris](https://scholaris.ca/) [https://scholaris.ca/] is illustrative - effectively a 'Trove for research' which indexes existing repositories. It prevents the unnecessary duplication of resourcing at individual institutions to develop repositories. A cross-walk capability can link metadata from existing functional repositories in institutions and academic organisations into the central repository. This will create a sovereign collection of our national research outputs, safeguarded from the geopolitical risks to our research outputs housed by institutions and companies overseas.

For any progress on effective rights retention to occur, the repository infrastructure across Australia will need a significant uplift. There has not been any federal investment in repositories since the Systemic Infrastructure Initiative in 2001, when funds were allocated to universities to build repositories to meet the reporting requirements of the then-proposed Research Quality Framework.

2. National infrastructure for academic-led open publishing

Repositories make research published behind commercial paywalls, along with data and other supporting materials, openly accessible. Another parallel infrastructure is institutional and academic-led Open Access publishing. 'Diamond' journals are free to read and free to publish, moving away from the 'pay to publish' model of Open Access. By strengthening Diamond Open Access there is a viable cost effective alternative to commercial publishing controlled by research communities. The [Operational Diamond OA Criteria](https://zenodo.org/records/12721408) for journals clearly defines the difference between Diamond Open Access and other journal models [https://zenodo.org/records/12721408].

Europe has been investing significantly in Diamond Open Access infrastructure, with [multiple European funders](https://zenodo.org/records/14626659) committing to support Diamond Open Access [https://zenodo.org/records/14626659]. The [European Diamond Capacity Hub](https://diameter.org/) [https://diameter.org/] was launched in January 2025 to Strengthen Diamond Open Access Publishing in Europe. The [Action Plan for Diamond Open Access](https://www.scienceeurope.org/our-resources/action-plan-for-diamond-open-access/) was published in 2022 by Science Europe, cOAlition S, OPERAS, and the French National Research Agency [https://www.scienceeurope.org/our-resources/action-plan-for-diamond-open-access/]. This has been endorsed by the [German funding body DFG](https://www.dfg.de/en/news/news-topics/announcements-proposals/2022/info-wissenschaft-22-26) [https://www.dfg.de/en/news/news-topics/announcements-proposals/2022/info-wissenschaft-22-26]. The Netherlands have [developed programs to strengthen Open Access nationally](https://ukb.nl/en/programmes/diamond-open-access/) [https://ukb.nl/en/programmes/diamond-open-access/].

There are some initiatives in Diamond Open Access in Australia - at individual institutional levels such as [QUT](https://www.library.qut.edu.au/openpress/journals/) [https://www.library.qut.edu.au/openpress/journals/] and [Sydney University](https://openjournals.library.sydney.edu.au/) [https://openjournals.library.sydney.edu.au/] and others [listed here](https://oaaustralasia.org/directory-type/open-journals/) [https://oaaustralasia.org/directory-type/open-journals/] and a [Community of Practice](https://oaaustralasia.org/australian-scholarly-communications-community-of-practice-diamond-journal-publishing-subgroup/) established by Open Access Australasia [https://oaaustralasia.org/australian-scholarly-communications-community-of-practice-diamond-journal-publishing-subgroup/]

These endeavours pale into insignificance in light of international efforts. Australia needs to develop national infrastructure and support for academy-led Open Access journal publication.

Action 3 - Improving the legal infrastructure around research publications and data at the institutional level

Australian default IP frameworks are limiting access to publicly funded research. Law and regulation has primarily been designed for privately funded corporate research, commercial products and consumers, to the neglect of consideration of rights management that facilitates collaboration and take up of research. Open infrastructure is far more nimble and responsive to specific research user information needs than a restrictive IP landscape that is controlled by commercial publishers who are largely indifferent to whether or not development of an innovative idea or collaboration proceeds, except as a means to extract a profit. Current legislative frameworks need to be reformed to better serve the Australian research community or facilitate research translation.

Much could be learned about the actual functioning of Australian research infrastructure from a comparative study of the international context, mapping the kinds of regulation and policies we lack, and how innovation culture is impacted due to this neglect. Australia has many more barriers to sharing research, research data and building collaborations than comparator countries due to three related factors:

1. No effective rights retention
2. Outdated IP commercialisation metrics
3. Poor understanding of the wider legal infrastructure supporting research collaboration

1. No effective rights retention

Universities reformed institutional IP Policy in the wake of *University of Western Australia v Gray* [2009] FCAFC 116 to strengthen employer claims to employee IP, after the university failed to enforce an ownership claim to the patent related to a cancer treatment granted to a former employee, Dr Gray. Independent analysis by Australian IP experts suggests that these reforms are not as effective as has been assumed (Bowrey, K., Cochrane, T., Hadley, M., McKeough, J., Pappalardo, K., & Weatherall, K. (2023). *Managing Ownership of Copyright in Research Publications to Increase the Public Benefits from Research*. *Federal Law Review*, 52(1), 3-33. [<https://doi.org/10.1177/0067205X231213676>].

First, university IP policies are not always clearly incorporated into employment contracts, complicating their legal efficacy. Second, the position in relation to ownership of **copyright and data** requires particular attention. University IP policies vary in relation to the ownership of employee-generated copyright. For example, some university policies claim ownership of copyright in research outputs; others say that authors are the first owners of copyright but retain a non-exclusive licence for certain university purposes. Many policies may not be effective in addressing the status of works created by researchers in non-research or other non-standard positions.

Default legal arrangements impact the legality of commercialisation and publishing agreements that would facilitate Open Access (OA) to research and free up access to outputs from behind paywalls. The former chief scientist, Dr Cathy Foley, recognised the huge cost of accessing Australian research as objectionable.

There is an easy way to clarify university ownership rights of employee works and to improve access to publicly funded research outputs. Australian universities need to adopt a harmonised approach to University IP Policy, that is, the same approach across all public universities, including clauses that secure institutional rights retention.

Rights retention

Rights retention provides legal support for Open Science. Effective rights retention enables authors (and their institutions) to:

- take control of their copyright and share their publications and data under an open licence
- encourage further reuse and gain wide exposure for their work, leading to increased engagement
- comply with Open Access requirements of major research funders, such as the World Health Organization, European Commission, Wellcome Trust, Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation, NHMRC and ARC
- Facilitate large-scale data analysis of research outputs by researchers and business to develop new innovations

Without effective rights retention, Australian authors may be required to assign copyright to the publisher. Publication contracts restrict the academics' ability to reuse their research, disseminate it further or produce derivative works for the benefit of new audiences. Problems will likely become more acute as AI tools become increasingly integrated into research processes. Publishers will control and commercialise research access to databases, largely compilations of publicly funded research outputs, and generate new profitable data analytics drawn from the academic use of these datasets. Australian researchers may find themselves locked out of the design and use of essential data analysis tools, limited by reliance on inadequate commercial datasets, and unable to trace information provenance or reliability.

University-level rights retention policies have been rolled out across many institutions across the globe. In the UK, these policies allow researchers to comply with funder requirements of Open Access without embargo and ensure publications are eligible for inclusion in the REF research assessment exercise. Since 2021, United Kingdom Research and Innovation ('UKRI') has made OA publication of journal articles mandatory. In many EU countries rights retention has been implemented in copyright legislation through a secondary right of publication (SRP). SRP has been enacted as an author's right that cannot be overridden by publication agreements; as an obligation on researchers who accept public funds; and as an exception to copyright infringement prohibiting publishers from pursuing academics for disseminating their own work (*Lazarova, A., (forthcoming), 'Conceptualising the Right to Secondary Publication' in Sganga, C. & Synodinou, T.E. (eds), Flexibilities in Copyright Law, Routledge, [\[https://ssrn.com/abstract=4934531\]](https://ssrn.com/abstract=4934531)*). Without Open Access and Open Data requirements in research assessment or legislation requiring the making available of research for broader use, Australian researchers are placed at a distinct disadvantage and engagement with Australian publicly funded R&D is inhibited. Through effective rights retention, UK and EU researchers in receipt of taxpayer funds are required to ensure there are no formal legal impediments to public access to research outputs.

Rights retention is pro-innovation because it removes legal impediments that artificially dissect research into separate markets – basic, applied, experimental and mission oriented research – subject to different and confusing restrictions on access. Restrictions on access may be necessary, for example, due to commercial confidentiality or to protect Indigenous Knowledge rights, but restrictions should be purposeful and serve the interests of research communities, not publishers.

2. Reliance on outdated IP commercialisation metrics to measure performance

The historical focus on innovation metrics using proxies such as number of patents and spin out companies was well recognised as problematic in a lengthy report written in 2019 by then Chief Scientist Alan Finkel, with Mark Cully: *Improving Innovation Indicators, DISR2022*: [<https://www.industry.gov.au/publications/innovation-metrics-review#final-report-3>].

IP Commercialisation

Contrary to a common perception that Australian universities are poor at innovation leading to IP commercialisation, IP Australia reports repeatedly show significant achievements by public institutions compared to industry in bringing research to patent filing stage. For example, the *IP Australia Australian Intellectual Property Report (2024)* lists public institutions making up five of the top ten resident applications: CSIRO, NewSouth Innovations, Monash University, Agriculture Victoria, RMIT. However, the proportion of domestic filings overall remains very low.

Despite high expectations of significant returns, in particular from biotechnology patents based on university research, there has been no cost benefit analysis considering the cost effectiveness of operating university IP Commercialisation divisions. In an Australian context where the majority of patents are foreign owned, the patent game creates obstacles for Australian researchers.

A rare qualitative study of patent impacts on Australian science found that Australian researchers spend a lot of time ‘working around’ patent issues and look to ‘academic cover’, hoping overly-broad foreign patents will not be enforced (*MacLennan, A. & Maslen, S. (2023). Impact of Patents on the Practice of Synthetic Biology in Australia: A Qualitative Study. Australian Intellectual Property Law Journal, 34:89*). University research culture in synthetic biology was described as naturally collaborative and open. The authors observe [at p93]:

Open innovation is also a potential solution to address these issues. Sharing of data between communities of scientists can be likened to sharing within communities of innovators in other fields such as information and computer technologies. Indeed, some synthetic biologists have drawn inspiration from the user generated solutions to copyright issues in that field. Theory suggests that innovation can be enhanced if users share data in a cooperative, organised way within “innovation communities”.

Freeing researchers from legal distractions that impede the progress of science requires Australian universities to harmonise their IP Policies, and include rights retention clauses to support Open Science practice.

Recent research by UQ Laureate Professor Brad Sherman (*Intangible, Intangibles. Patent Law's Engagement with Dematerialised Subject Matter, Cambridge University Press, 2024*) clearly demonstrates the significance of the role of academic scientists in developing the essential information that allows new patent subject matter to be visualised, defined, and explained to enable the patent system to function to support breakthrough innovation. Academic scientists, working collaboratively and supported by international professional organisations and learned academies, render breakthrough patent subject matter legible and manageable. When this occurs patent rights are more clearly bounded and further research and development can take place with less risk. This understanding of the close interconnection between science and law has real world implications for science and technology policy and the patent system. A productive role can be played by the patent system in securing rights to innovation when there is support for development of professionalisation of new expertise, global networks, information flows and knowledge curation that is needed to manage the challenges of new intangible subject matter. Government needs to more holistically address the constitution of the knowledge infrastructure that links researchers engaged in basic, applied and mission-oriented research and builds connections across disciplines. A better understanding of and Australian engagement with Open Science is useful here because global policy initiatives such as the UNESCO Open Science Recommendation, are designed to improve access to research and data and build the research communities which Sherman identifies as necessary to create the context for coherent and predictable patent rights, operating in sync with industry's developing needs.

Spin out companies

The UK Department for Business, Energy, and Industrial Strategy (BEIS) conducted (2018) a large study into university IP commercialisation (*RMS Consulting, Research into issues around the commercialisation of university IP*.

[<https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/5acf1bcee5274a76c13df8e5/university-ip-commercialisation-research.pdf>]. Research involved 138 interviews with representatives from 35 universities (senior management and technology transfer or knowledge exchange staff); 291 interviews with businesses, charities and spin-outs; and 20 interviews with investors. A key lesson from that review is that interpersonal relationships are critical to successful commercialisation to develop relationships between an academic inventor, companies, and investors, to build the working relationship that contribute to the long-term success of commercialisation and positive outcomes such as follow-on licencing deals, research collaborations, or consultancy relationships. Building relationships requires a research culture and academic career assessment that more strongly supports external engagement and creation of research outputs in formats suitable for industry and community.

Another finding was that due to the *inadequate funding of research within universities there are internal pressures to produce the big ticket win from commercialisation*. In the UK this pressure increased concern within universities about underpricing or undervaluing IP. Such concerns complicated relationship building and put pressure on IP commercialisation staff to report wins and assert IP ownership in scenarios well before any realistic market potential of an industry collaboration could be assessed. A poorly implemented pro-commercialisation research culture creates undue pressures on university commercialisation offices and researchers, which leads to a sidelining of consideration of the far more complex commercial conditions required to generate profit from patents.

The UK's Department of Science, Innovation and Technology/HM Treasury (2023) *Independent Study of University Spin Out Companies* :

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/6549fcb23ff5770013a88131/independent_review_of_university_spin-out_companies.pdf] similarly identified that universities struggle with the costs of operating technology transfer offices (TTOs) from spin-out income.

Outdated and inappropriate IP commercialisation metrics used in the context where university research is not fully funded, leads to an expensive IP infrastructure with uncertain rewards or benefits to universities, inventors or external partners. An independent review of costs and benefits of university IP commercialisation, including the costs on researchers of having to work around patents, is overdue.

3. Poor understanding of the wider legal infrastructure supporting research collaboration

Barriers that impede the impact of Open Science have been described as related to a lack of skills, resources and infrastructure to effectively re-use and build on existing research (Klebel, T. Traag, V., Grypari, J., Stoy, L., Ross-Hellauer, T. (2025) *The academic impact of Open Science: a scoping review*. *Roy.Soc.Open Sci* 12(3) [<https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.241248>]. Other nations have studied, and are further developing, the legal infrastructure required to support Open Science. Compared to other countries Australia has conducted very little research into the legal infrastructure supporting research collaboration.

The largest published empirical study is the European Commission (2024) *Study to evaluate the effects of the EU copyright framework on research and the effects of potential interventions and to identify and present relevant provisions for research in EU data and digital legislation, with a focus on rights and obligations* [DOI: [10.2777/633395](https://doi.org/10.2777/633395)]. This study combines desk research with stakeholder interviews to identify how law and policy operated in practice. It concludes with recommendations to the private sector, researchers and research organisations, law and policy makers in management of the following areas: Open Data Directive; Data Governance Act; Digital Service Act; Digital Markets Act; Data Act; AI Act; European Open Science Cloud.

The absence of copyright law reform is a longstanding problem as identified by the Australian Law Reform Commission Report, *Copyright and the Digital Economy* (2014) and the Productivity Commission (2017) *Inquiry into Intellectual Property Arrangements*. IPAustralia has no significant copyright or data expertise and limited interest in publicly funded research and infrastructure. While the Attorney General's *Copyright and Artificial Intelligence Reference Group* (CAIRG) has partial oversight of data issues as they pertain to AI technologies, unlike the EU, Australia remains at a disadvantage due to a highly restrictive status quo and the absence of any dedicated consideration of what copyright and data laws would best serve the national interest to deliver a robust, pro innovation research infrastructure.

Comparative benchmarking, analysing barriers to accessing and reusing publicly funded research, and evaluating the contribution of copyright and data legislation would provide a more comprehensive overview of Australia's research and innovation legal landscape, providing insights for policymakers, researchers, research organisations and external collaborators.

Action 4 - Embedding of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Knowledge in mainstream knowledge systems

Addressing the current fragmented approach to the inclusion of Indigenous Knowledge to embed Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander research processes in the R&D system requires a deeper consideration of:

1. Improved protection of Indigenous Cultural and Intellectual Property (ICIP) and Indigenous data sovereignty
 2. Indigenous governance of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander knowledge
1. Improved protection of ICIP and Indigenous data sovereignty

Elevating Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islanders knowledge systems is an important national science priority. Australia celebrates the deep history and knowledge systems embedded in Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples, cultures and Countries. Within universities and businesses, the science and research system is slowly evolving to protect and elevate Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Knowledge. This is coming about by building practices that weave in Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Knowledge, where implementation respects Indigenous governance practices facilitated by Indigenous Cultural and Intellectual Property (ICIP) and Indigenous data sovereignty protocols.

By taking this step First Nations' Peoples can share specific cultural and scientific knowledge with research communities because it is safe to do so. However, the legal framework remains rudimentary at best. The significance of law reform suggestions are also often overstated. For example, IP Australia's work streams in the protection and management of First Nations' knowledge are designed to encourage sharing of knowledge but fall short of recommending patent invalidity when Indigenous Knowledge is appropriated by the inventor. Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Peoples' well-established and sophisticated systems for trading knowledge are marginalised and undermined by the Australian legal system. Efforts to embed Aboriginal and Torres Strait Island research processes in the system will not deliver positive results if we cannot move past a nod to protocols. Protocols are generally silent on enforcement or can only be enforced as ethics or contractual breaches where the relevant Australian institution or court would determine breach and consequences according to relevant institutional governance or mainstream Australian IP law.

2. Indigenous governance of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander knowledge

Australian Indigenous Advisory Groups have been used as a mechanism to advise the government on policies and legislation influencing Indigenous communities. Australian Indigenous Advisory Groups are political models where the rule of engagement is dictated by the dominant culture in 'consultation' with the Indigenous community. Such practices erode Aboriginal models of engagement and community discussion is replaced more and more with the dominant 'voice'. Missing from these discussions is the 'proppa' voices of Aboriginal people, as determined by Indigenous governance mechanisms. The

selective appointment of Aboriginal leaders to committees as 'representative' of communities, nations or races fills a void in representation. It does not advance the embedding of Indigenous Knowledge.

Mainstreaming Indigenous governance of Indigenous Knowledges within research institutions and in businesses will position Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples to lead research that affects them – as community leaders, traditional knowledge holders and researchers.